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Music for Francesco II D'Este

Prince of Music

G. BONONCINI
G.M. BONONCINI
G. COLOMBI
D. GABRIELLI
P.N. SOROSINA
G.B. VITALI

Sofia Pezzi *soprano*
Ettore Agati *countertenor*
Giovanni Paganelli *direction*

 Modena Barocca

Music for FRANCESCO II D'ESTE Prince of Music / Principe della Musica

(Modena, 1660 - Sassuolo, 1694)

Musica dedicata a Francesco II D'Este

GIOVANNI BATTISTA VITALI

1632-1692

Sonata No.1 for violin and B.C.

From *Artifici musicali, opera decima terza*

(Modena, Cassiani, 1689, copy in I-MOe Mus. D. 530)

- | | |
|----------------|------|
| 1. I. Largo | 1'36 |
| 2. II. Allegro | 1'16 |
| 3. II. | 1'15 |
| 4. IV. | 0'35 |
| 5. V. | 1'07 |

«Coronata d'applausi»

for soprano*, 3 violins and B.C.

Cantata per l'accademia sopra la nascita di Sua Altezza Serenissima

(ms. I-MOe Mus. E. 1261, No.1)

- | | |
|--|------|
| 6. Recitativo «Coronata d'applausi» | 0'35 |
| 7. Aria «Per freggiare un sol che nasce» | 1'11 |
| 8. Recitativo «Doppo lieve contesa» | 0'38 |

- | | |
|--|------|
| 9. Aria «Sì bel giorno più splendido e adorno» | 0'51 |
| 10. Recitativo «Già l'Invidia e la Sorte» | 0'23 |
| 11. Aria «Godan gl'astri e rida il sole» | 1'07 |
| 12. Recitativo «Sì disse e fe' ritorno» | 0'29 |

GIUSEPPE COLOMBI 1635-1694

13. *Ciaccona for violoncello and B.C.*

(mss. I-MOe Mus. E. 350 /

Mus. F. 283) 2'50

14. «Di Lidia al sen vezzoso»

Cantata for soprano and B.C.*

(ms. I-MOe Mus. E. 281, No.7) 1'52

GIOVANNI MARIA BONONCINI

1642-1678

15. **Giga La Cimicella**

From *Arie, correnti, sarabande, gighe e allemande a violino e violone, over spinetta, con alcune intavolate per diverse accordature* (Bologna, Giacomo Monti, 1671, esemplare I-Bc X.112) 1'15

16. **Sarabanda** 0'40

Cleopatra Moribonda

*Cantata for soprano** and B.C.*

From *Cantate per camera a voce sola, libro primo, opera decima* (Bologna, Giacomo Monti, 1677, copy in I-MOe Mus. G.20)

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|--|------|
| 17. Recitativo «Per non calcar di Roma» | 1'15 |
| 18. Aria Allegro «Che mi giova di Fortuna» | 1'54 |
| 19. Recitativo «Di diane, di febi» | 1'33 |

- | | |
|--|------|
| 20. Aria Vivo «Ma che pensi, Fortuna crudele» | 1'19 |
| 21. Recitativo «Schiava non mi vedrai» | 1'00 |
| 22. Aria Vivace «Non trarrò già scalzo il piè» | 1'15 |
| 23. Recitativo «Sì, che morirò da forte» | 1'42 |
| 24. Aria Vago «Oh, dell'aspe che 'l seno m'ancide» | 1'58 |
| 25. Recitativo «Ma già con piè veloce» | 2'05 |

DOMENICO GABRIELLI 1659-1690

«Amor m'hai così avinto»

Cantata for soprano and B.C.*

From *Cantate a voce sola* (Bologna, Pier Maria Monti, 1691, copy in I-Bc Z.181)

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|--|------|
| 26. Recitativo «Amor, m'hai così avinto» | 0'57 |
|--|------|

- | | | | |
|---|------|--|------|
| 27. Aria Andante «Se a guardar
bellezze amabili» | 1'33 | 33. Aria Vivace «Dunque amor le
sue facelle» | 2'16 |
| 28. Recitativo «Ma, almen s'altro
non posso» | 0'32 | 34. Recitativo «Sarò sempre
costante» | 0'24 |
| 29. Aria Allegro «Amanti,
quel volto» | 1'08 | 35. Vivace e a battuta «Che lusinga
e inganna/che consola e
diletta e l'alma e il core» | 2'51 |
| 30. Recitativo «Ah, che se
alcun vedessi» | 1'05 | | |
| GIOVANNI BONONCINI 1670-1747
«Il nume d'amore»
<i>Duet for canto, * alto** and B.C.</i>
From <i>Duetti da camera, opera ottava</i>
(Bologna, Pier Maria Monti, 1691 copy
in I-MOe Mus. F.100) | | PIETRO NICOLÒ SOROSINA
c.1645-1732
36. <i>Gelosia invidiosa</i>
Duet for 2 sopranos*/**
(mss. I-MOe Mus. F. 1377,
No.13/ Mus. F. 1091) | 3'51 |
| 31. Aria Adagio «Il nume d'amore» | 4'26 | | |
| 32. Recitativo «Han sì veloce
moto le saette» | 1'03 | | |

Sofia Pezzi *soprano** · Ettore Agati *countertenor***

MODENA BAROCCA

Antonio De Sarlo *first violin and solo* · Beatrice Scaldini, Linda Priebbenow *violin*
Marco Anginella *cello and bass violin*
Federico Lanzellotti *organ and musicological research*
Giovanni Paganelli *harpsichord, direction and conducting*

«*Un vago accoppiamento d'aria dolce e insieme di maestà*»
Francesco II d'Este, the prince of music

Francesco II d'Este ruled over his duchy from 1674 to 1694, two decades that proved to be of exceptional importance for the musical history of Modena.

The duke's profound interest gave rise to a great upsurge in music composition, performance and conservation. Hence, the historian Ludovico Antonio Muratori, — who described the prince of d'Este as «*bellissimo d'aspetto, con un vago accoppiamento d'aria dolce, e insieme di maestà*» (“extraordinarily handsome, with a charming combination of sweetness and majesty”) and captured Francesco II's passion for horses and for literature — referred that: «*al pari di qualsivoglia maestro era egli intendente della musica e però a' servigi suoi ebbe con grosso salario i più accreditati musici di que' tempi*» (“He equalled all teachers in his understanding of music e yet he paid high salaries to have at his service the most renowned musicians of the time”) [*Delle Antichità estensi continuazione, o sia parte seconda*, Modena 1760, p. 601].

Second son of Duke Alfonso IV d'Este and of “mazarinette” Laura Martinozzi (her uncle was Cardinal Mazzarino, hence the epithet), Francesco II was born on 6 March 1660. From an early age he showed an interest in music, taking violin lessons from the *vicemaestro* Giuseppe Colombi (1635-1694), and becoming an expert amateur, a patron of literature and the arts, a bibliophile and a learned collector.

In turning his court and city into a productive cultural centre of European appeal, Francesco II surrounded himself with musicians of quality, keeping abreast of all the musical styles, genres and tastes of the time. Exceptional composers, singers and instrumentalists headed for Modena, and some of them, such as Giovanni Battista Vitali (1632-1692) or Domenico Gabrielli (1659-1690), moved there permanently, while others chose to spend in this city only a part of their career. There were also musicians, such as Giovanni Bononcini, who started their paths in Modena and later went on to perform in the main musical centres of Europe.

When Francesco II came to power, the ducal chapel (reinstated by his mother in 1671) expanded to comprise at least twenty-nine members by the year 1689. Proudly described in a letter to his sister Maria Beatrice as «*una capella di musici, e suonatori, che supera tutte l'altre d'Italia*» (“a chapel of musicians and players, that surpasses all others in Italy”), it was run under his direct supervision. Moreover, Francesco II created a network for hiring the musicians and was in contact with many eminent composers and virtuoso players of the period, including Arcangelo Corelli, who he had heard in Rome in 1686.

The entire cultural and musical life of the city revolved around the duke and developed alongside the ducal palace and the delightful summer residence at Sassuolo (where even a *peschiera* or pool could be included in performances) and other musical institutions such as the city Cathedral.

During those years also the theatre in Modena greatly gained in impetus. The Teatro Valentini, which was burned down in January 1681, reopened in 1685 thanks to the marquis Decio Fontanelli, who was able to take it over thanks to a considerable loan from the duke. Perfectly renewed to host opera productions, the city theatre embodied the close collaboration between the duke and Fontanelli: Francesco II was able to use it as an expression of his power, and at the same time gratify his own personal desire to operate behind the scenes. Thus, when in 1686 the new court theatre was opened, the duke could count on the overall direction of Francesco Stringa, the Modenese «*sovrintendente alle fabbriche ducali*» (“supervisor of ducal buildings”), as well as the contribution of eminent specialists in stage design such as the Bolognese Gian Giacomo Monti and Francesco Bibiena. In 1682 the duke also re-established the University in Modena, thereby expanding and restoring its earlier *Studium*, as well as promoting the development of the Accademia dei Dissonanti, described by its members as a «*parto totale del gran genio del prencipe*» (“entirely due to the great genius of the prince”).

All the fashionable musical genres of the period were performed at court and in

the city. Particular attention was devoted to the oratorio, a reflection of the duke's personal education and the surrounding moral climate influenced by the Theatines and by the figure of the Jesuit father Andrea Garimberti. Yet instrumental music and chamber cantata enjoyed great consideration. The outcome was a significant number of volumes of instrumental pieces that were dedicated to Francesco II, including several by the Bononcini, by Colombi and Vitali, as well as the *Sonate a tre opera terza* by Corelli and the *Concertino per camera opera quarta* by Torelli. Furthermore, the rich collection of cantatas kept in the Estense Library comprises a considerable number of works relating to the activities of the Accademia. A case in point is the cantata by G. B. Vitali «*Sopra la nascita di S. A. S.*» (Tracks 6-12), composed to celebrate the duke's birthday.

Moreover, during Francesco II's duchy the ducal library continued to grow, acquiring an increasingly important collection of scores and greatly contributing to the cultural history of Modena. The collection started out as a remarkable nucleus of manuscript and printed works compiled earlier in Ferrara prior to the devolution and moved to Modena; there, it was enriched during the years of Francesco II with numerous music books and scores. The tendency towards systematic documentation of musical activity invested both the Modena and Reggio areas and elsewhere, including the main musical centres of the period, such as Rome, Venice and Bologna. This led to the conservation of the performing scores; to the production of copies as required (largely made by local copyists); to the purchase of volumes from other important collections, such as that of Alessandro Stradella.

The librarian at this august institution during the early decades of the 18th century was Muratori, who clearly admired Francesco II's love of books: «*E intendo ben io di pagare un tributo di gratitudine alle belle idee di questo assennato principe con ricordare ai posteri che la Biblioteca Estense, ricca di tanti libri stampati e manuscritti, a lui dee l'origine sua; e che maggiore accrescimento avrebbe ben essa ricevuto, se la morte sì tosto non avesse troncato il filo della sua vita, e de' suoi*

magnifici disegni» (“And I intend to pay a tribute of thanks to the fine ideas of this enlightened prince by reminding posterity that the Estense Library, with its wealth of printed books and manuscripts, owes its origins to him; and that it would have grown even larger if premature death had not severed the thread of his life and of his magnificent projects”) [*Delle Antichità estensi continuazione, o sia parte seconda*, Modena 1740, p. 601].

Follow some essentials regarding the works recorded in this CD and the composers who wrote them, all of whom in one way or another were connected with the city and the duke. **Giovanni Battista Vitali** was born in Bologna but lived and worked in Modena from 1674, devoting many compositions to the court. The *Artifici musicali*, dedicated to the duke in 1689, play a central role in his output. They consist of around sixty pieces devised as an aid to mastering counterpoint and exploring musical systems, styles and forms. The *Suonata prima* for violin and basso continuo (tracks 1-5), features juxtaposition of the *cantabile* melodic style of the first and third movements with the imitation patterns of the second and fifth and the cheerful, dance-like mood of the fourth.

Vitali was a prudent but skilful innovator, who also wrote vocal music. Catalogued under Mus. F. 1261, the Estense Library holds a manuscript volume that comprises six *accademias* (celebrative cantatas for performance within the sphere of the Accademia). Inaugurates the collection the cantata «*Coronata d'applausi di Francesco il natale*», composed «*per l'accademia sopra la nascita di Sua Altezza Serenissima*» (“for the academy on the birth of His Most Serene Highness”), whose confident but courteous vocal line is accompanied by three violins and basso continuo that create an intricate texture. Although the author of the verse is unknown, he is likely to have belonged to the *dissonante* circle. Reminiscent of Tasso, the epithet «*azio eroe*» in the aria «*Godan gl'astri e rida il sole*» (track 11) is also found in Zefiro and Flora's eulogistic *Prologo*, added to the opera *L'Alcibiade* and dedicated to the duke by Carlo Bertini (Teatro Ducale, 1685).

Giuseppe Colombi focused largely on instrumental music, leaving posterity with a substantial legacy of manuscript music, mainly of instrumental works, which are now the object of complex attribution studies. Apart from various pieces for basso *solo*, including the well-known *Ciaccona* (track 13), the Estense Library also comprises at least three cantatas (mss. Mus. E. 281, Mus. F. 1385), that reveal in their boldly angular melodic scape the audacious instrumental style of the composer. The cantata «*Di Lidia al sen vezzoso*» (track 14) — maybe part of a more complex work — consists of a short recitative that introduces the song of Aurillo. The variety of poetic rhythm and meter is translated into a musical form featuring a series of short musical episodes in different tempos.

Father of the three brothers Giovanni, Antonio Maria and Giovanni Maria *junior* (known as Angelo), **Giovanni Maria Bononcini** (1642-1678) was a prolific composer and the author of a widely known treatise: *Il musico pratico* (Bologna 1673, and various reprints). The collection of *Arie, correnti, sarabande, gigue e allemande a violino e violone, over spinetta, con alcune intavolate per diverse accordature* (Bologna, Giacomo Monti, 1671) comprises a number of dance movements, characteristic of the Italian-French mixed style that was fashionable at court. They include the Giga *La Cimicella* and the following Sarabanda (tracks 15-16), which radiate brio and rhythmic verve.

In 1673, two years after joining the duke's *concerto degli stromenti*, Bononcini was appointed chapel master in the cathedral. He remained in Modena for the rest of his days, dedicating various works to Francesco II. These included the *Cantate per camera a voce sola, libro primo, opera decima*, printed in Bologna in 1677 by Giacomo Monti. Part of this collection, the cantata *Cleopatra moribonda* shows a fascinating poetic text by Giulio Cesare Grassetti. The shimmering rhyme patterns and meters suggested a flexible structure and rhythm, marked by the refrain «*Morrò misera sì: vincesti, oh Sorte*» that returns and evolves during the course of the cantata. Bononcini translates the defeated queen's suffering into a piece based on chiaroscuro, that underlines the extreme poignancy of her feelings.

The first recitative (track 17) is a brief introduction to Cleopatra's extensive monologue, beginning with her disconsolate aria «*Che mi giova*» (track 18). In the following «*Ma che pensi, Fortuna crudele*» (track 20), despondency gradually gives way to determination and then rebellion against fate which vehemently emerge in the following recitative «*Schiava non mi vedrai*» (track 21). The proud sovereign has been defeated, but she will not be led to Rome as a slave: she will kill herself, and in so doing she will preserve her self-determination. Transfigured by the power of this decision, Cleopatra sings the aria «*Non trarrò già scalzo il piè*» (track 22). Bononcini emphasises her claim for freedom by using the major key, the ternary meter and a proud melodic path which highlights the truncated lines. Marked *Vago*, the next unexpectedly mellifluous aria «*Oh, dell'aspe che 'l seno m'ancide*» (track 24) elevates the tragedy of suicide, investing it with sensuality as the dying queen longs for the "sweetness" of deadly poison. The venom begins to take hold, and the hallucinating Cleopatra sings her last, hugely powerful recitative (track 25), celebrating her victory over her enemy, fate and death as she conjures up worldly vanity and consigns her legend to eternity.

Domenico Gabrielli was born in Bologna but studied under G. Legrenzi in Venice. He moved to Modena in 1688, at the height of a career as opera composer and cellist. The cantata «*Amore m'hai così avinto*», published posthumously in 1691 can be considered a "study of jealousy". The irrational, pathological protectiveness blinds the protagonist leading him to fear that his beloved, whose countenance is as white as snow, might melt in the sun. Gabrielli handles this insightful poetic hyperbole with an extended double flourish (track 26). In the following two strophic arias the lover expresses his desire to follow his beloved everywhere (track 27) and to shield her from the gaze of other men (tracks 28-29). The last recitative underlines the obsessive nature of the feelings at work: the lover begins to fear even himself, and in the final Adagio confesses with astonishment that his heart and indeed his eyes «*son gelosi fra loro*» (track 30).

Giovanni Bononcini (1670-1747), the eldest of Giovanni Maria's three sons, dedicated the first fruits of his vast output to Francesco II. From an early age he studied under the composer Giovanni Paolo Colonna in Bologna, where he published his first six collections of instrumental music between 1685 and 1687. They begin with the *Trattenimenti da camera opera prima*, the first in a series of homages to Francesco II, who would appear to have followed the young musician's progress with unflinching interest. In 1687, when the seventeen-years-old Bononcini was already a member of the Accademia Filarmonica (May 1686) and of the Chapel of San Petronio in Bologna, the duke made sure that he was appointed chapel master at the church of San Giovanni in Monte. Subsequently, as further proof of the fact that Bononcini maintained a close relationship with this city during the years of his musical training, his first two oratorios, *La vittoria di Davide contro Golia* (1687) and *Il Giosuè* (1688), were performed in Modena. Then, the duke commissioned a third oratorio: *La Maddalena a' piedi di Cristo* (1690).

On the contrary, the first edition of the *Duetti da camera* was dedicated to the Emperor Leopold I of Habsburg, an homage paid off a few years later, when Bononcini was appointed imperial composer and awarded a very high salary. The *Duetti* brought him renown and widely circulated over the next decades. The second of the collection, *Il nume d'amore*, consists of two alternated arias and recitatives followed by an extensive contrapuntal development of the last *a due* hendecasyllable (track 35). The opening aria (track 31) features a spontaneously flowing melody, some harmonic harshness and a refined bass part. Indeed, as John E. Galliard declared in the early 1700s, Bononcini was renowned for his «agreeable and easie style, and those fine inventions in his basses (to which he was led by an instrument upon which he excells)». The aria «*Dunque amor le sue facelle*» (track 33) makes effective use of the rhythmic impulse created by harmonic repeated developing patterns and anacrusis, revealing great mastery of the pedal and of darting figurations in semiquavers to create the impression of lightning.

The CD ends with the duet «*Gelosia, co' tuoi sospetti*» by Pietro Nicolò Sorosina (c. 1645-1732), that recalls the subject of jealousy (track 36). The Estense Library comprises one of the very few collections of music by Sorosina, who was in the employ of the Habsburgs around 1677, initially in the service of Empress Eleonora Maddalena Gonzaga-Nevers, widow of Ferdinand III, and thereafter in that of the Holy Roman Emperor Leopold I. The poem set to music consists of six lines that are handled with a *da capo* (verses 1-2) followed by a contrastive section. The first couplet (lines 3-4) comes across as a continuation of the *da capo*, reiterating its character, whereas the latter couplet (lines 5-6) acts as a firmly modulated musical contrast that underlines the gnomic nature of the last hendecasyllable.

Recent investigations have revealed that the lines set to music by Sorosina are in fact the first verse of a longer poem by Giovanni Pietro Monesio, *Gelosia invidiosa*. It was published in the collection *La musa seria*, dedicated to Leopold I of Habsburg (Corvo e Lupardi, Rome 1674). Sorosina may have set the entire poem to music, or merely selected the opening verse. A further example of this latter option is to be found in the duet «*Mio cor sta per morire*» (included in the manuscript collection Mus. F. 1093 in the Estense Library), which also involves just a portion of a much longer poem in Monesio's *La musa seria*.

The range of vocal and instrumental compositions included in this CD provides an enticing glimpse of musical life in Modena during the duchy of Francesco II. The project has involved in-depth study of 17th century musical sources kept in particular in the Estense University Library in Modena. In the footsteps of Muratori, we naturally express our own final thanks to Francesco II d'Este: this CD is also the fruit of his love of beauty and his desire to preserve and entrust to posterity an inestimable musical heritage.

© Federico Lanzellotti (Bologna, July 2020)

Translation by Kate Singleton

SOFIA PEZZI - *Soprano*

Born in Genoa in 1989, she obtained in 2016 a second level diploma in singing at the Paganini Conservatoire in Genoa. She attended several master classes with outstanding singers such as Vivica Genaux, her current teacher. She won first prize at the Premio Fatima Terzo 2017. In Rome in 2018, she took part in *Enea in Caonia*, by J. A. Hasse, she was Sesto in Handel's *Giulio Cesare in Egitto* and Zerlina in Mozart's *Don Giovanni*. She won the international singing competition “Lirica sul Tevere” for the staging of G. Rossini's *La Cenerentola*. Her schedule involves work with artists from Genoa specialized in early music, such as the Vox Dogalis ensemble and Accademia degli Imperfetti, devoted to the profane medieval and Renaissance repertoire.

ETTORE AGATI - *Countertenor*

Born in Iglesias in 1990, he graduated in singing at the Palestrina Conservatoire in Cagliari. He has won various competitions including the XI Premio Nazionale delle Arti Claudio Abbado, the Premio Sardegna and the Premio Fatima Terzo. He has taken part in the Festival degli Strumenti Antichi in Cagliari, festival Spazio&Musica in Vicenza, and festival Grandezze & Meraviglie in Modena. Accompanied by the Stradella Consort, he sang the role of Fede in the San Filippo Neri Oratorio by A. Scarlatti. He was also soloist in performances of Carmina Burana by Orff conducted by J. Bernàcer. He was Testo in Viano's staging of Monteverdi's *Il combattimento di Tancredi e Clorinda*, and Conte Nastri in *La Diavolessa* by Galuppi. He has recorded the first modern performance of *Mottetti Concertati* by Capece and Capuana with the vocal-instrumental ensemble Raræ Musicæ.

GIOVANNI PAGANELLI – *Harpsichord, direction and conducting*

Born in Modena, he studied Harpsichord and Organ at the Conservatorio Arrigo Boito in Parma. He then obtained the Master Musik in Harpsichord and the Master Musik in Fortepiano at the Musikhochschule Freiburg im Breisgau, where he is PhD candidate with a research project on D. Scarlatti. Since 2015, he works with Grandezze & Meraviglie, conducting the *Modena Barocca* ensemble. His first recording with Brilliant Classics in 2018 was *the Divertimenti da Camera tradotti pel Cembalo* by G. Bononcini. As a harpsichord soloist he took part in the Oude Muziek festival in Utrecht in 2019. He performs freelance as a harpsichordist and keyboardist with various groups in Europe. He is periodically involved in guides to musical awareness and listening. He founded and directs the Euphonia Music School.

FEDERICO LANZELLOTTI – *Organ and musicological research*

Born in Messina in 1994, he graduated in Piano and Early Keyboards with a thesis on Northern-Italy basso continuo (17th century). He obtained his MD at the University of Bologna, working on the critical edition of G. Bononcini's *Euleo festeggiante* (Vienna, 1699), which is currently being published by the Fondazione Arcadia (Milan). He works with Collezione Tagliavini, Teatro Comunale, «Il Saggiatore musicale» (Bologna), Festival Grandezze & Meraviglie (Modena) and with the Brilliant and CPO labels. He is part of the *alumni* of Fondazione “Levi” in Venice and is involved in the “Tartini2020” project. He combines musicological research and concert performance and is currently working on a co-tutored PhD in musicology at the University of Bologna and the Universidad Complutense of Madrid with a project on violin works by Carlo Ambrogio Lonati.

MODENA BAROCCA

The Ensemble was created by Grandezze & Meraviglie Festival to enhance the musical heritage preserved in the Estense Library in Modena, with its outstanding collection of manuscripts from the Middle Ages to the 18th century. The goal is to coordinate and integrate research, performance, publication and recording of Estense music, thereby discovering more about the musicians linked to the Este court in Modena and bringing the repertoire to the attention of festivals and musicological debate. The project involves young professionals and researchers with a solid academic background who have already made a name for themselves on the international music scene. The project is directed by harpsichordist Giovanni Paganelli and musicologist and keyboardist Federico Lanzellotti, under the coordination of Enrico Bellei.

Recording: 18-20 November 2019, Forum Monzani, Modena, Italy

A production by Festival Grandezze & Meraviglie

Artistic director: Enrico Bellei

Project administrator: Riccardo Andolina

Musicologic researcher: Federico Lanzellotti

Musical director and postproduction: Giovanni Paganelli

Record producer: Elisa Bestetti

Sound engineer: Giuseppe Tisi

Cover photo: Andrea Baratta (Carrara 1639-documentato dal 1657 al 1700)

Busto del duca Francesco II d'Este 1685 Sassuolo, Palazzo Ducale (foto Carlo Vannini)

[Courtesy of Gallerie Estensi - Modena Sassuolo Ferrara]

Artist photos: Giorgio Giliberti

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SUNG TEXTS

Cantata a soprano solo «Per l'Accademia sopra la nascita di S. A. S.»

(poetic text by Anonymous)

Coronata d'applausi
di Francesco il natale
già portato alle stelle avea la Fama,
quando il grido immortale
per celebrare il giorno
di sì eccelsa memoria
fra i pianeti destò garre di gloria.

Per freggiare un sol che nasce
s'indoraro il crin le stelle.
A infiorar l'argentea fasce
scintillarono più belle.

Doppo lieve contesa
ad illustrar la cuna
all'auriga del dì sorti l'impresa,
onde dal quarto giro
così lieto parlò oltre il costume
con accenti di gloria il dio del lume:

«Si bel giorno più splendido e adorno
chiaro il sole ne indori fedel.
Celebrare sia vanto immortale
d'un alcide il natale,
di chi i mostri calpesta sul ciel.

Già l'Invidia e la Sorte
fin là, bambino in fasce,
strozzò, vinse e confuse
e più ch'a un'idra il suo natal prelude.

Godan gl'astri e rida il sole
l'azio eroe se al mondo uscì.
Sol mi duole ch'a illustrare
un sì gran nome
splendin poco le mie chiome
entro il giro d'un sol di.»

Si disse e fe' ritorno
su l'Oriente a far più vago il giorno.

Cantata a soprano solo «Di Lidia al sen vezzoso»

(poetic text by Anonymous)

Di Lidia al sen vezzoso
Aurillo un dì s'affisse
in estasi d'amor e così disse:

«Gigli, ligustri e gelsomini, a dio!
Il vostro candore
con degno rossore
si ponga in oblio.
Tacete, cedete
a sen sì seren,
ch'in un petto d'amor bianco tesoro
d'ogni candido fior l'estratto adoro.»

Cantata Cleopatra moribonda a soprano solo
(«Poesia del Sig. Dottore Giulio Cesare Grasseti»)

Per non calcar di Roma
gl'abborriti confini
da servili catene oppressa e doma,
già de' Marti latini
la trionfante ogn'or venere altera

che su l'Egitto impera,
prima che d'ora estrema
rechi l'avviso ancor egro sopore,
tal prorompe, sfogando il suo dolore:
«Morrò misera, sì: vincesti, oh Sorte!

Che mi giova di Fortuna
il favor che non durò,
bel destin di nobile cuna,
se nel fin poi si cangiò?

Mio trofeo
fu Pompeo,
m'a che pro?
Che mi giova di Fortuna
il favor che non durò?
Ubbidi mie leggi amante,
de' Quirriti il dittatore,
un triumviro imperante
il mio cenno ebbe signore,
sue vittorie
fur mie glorie,
m'a che pro?
Che mi giova di Fortuna
il favor che non durò?

Di diane, di febi
mi vantai genitrice,
sovrana imperatrice.
Dove l'indica Teti il sole indora
vidi vassalla al mio voler l'Aurora,
ad un cenno ridutti
duo mondi a duellar, scherzi de' flutti.
Ma tutto, ah, che fu vano!
Non vinsi l'alma sol d'un Ottaviano.
Nulla più non sarà che mi conforte.
Morrò misera, sì: vincesti, oh Sorte!

Ma che pensi, Fortuna crudele,
contro l'egizia grande reina
mortale rovina
armando, incitando,
d'ogni mia gloria poter trionfare,
esultare?
T'inganni, t'inganni:
non appieno tuoi gusti tiranni
sazierai, bench'io sparga querele.

Schiava non mi vedrai
seguir la trionfale
pompa del tuo diletto Augusto. Il fiero
non con ciglio severo
condurrà catenata
Cleopatra animata.
Fia 'l mio destin men duro,
purché la libertà meco ne porte.
Morrò misera, sì: vincesti, oh Sorte!

Non trarrò già scalzo il piè
pellegrin nel Campidoglio,
cui sul patrio egizio soglio
fu vassallo più d'un re.
No ch'avvinta non andrò
ad ornar trionfo ingiusto:
non vedrà sua serva Augusto
chi monarchi già legò.

Si, che morirò da forte.
No, schiava non sarò, s'hai vinto, oh Sorte!
Ahi, ma quante cagioni
essacerban pur troppo i miei martiri!
Figli, voi, del mio bene
cari pegni adorati e di me stessa
parti, parte più viva, eppur sarete

spettacolo in mia vece
di vil plebe romana egizio gioco?
D'Africa il sol garzone,
la niliaca Diana
fia che nudi, oh destino,
annodi al carro suo Marte latino?

Oh, dell'aspe che 'l seno m'ancide
più cruccio pensiero insofribile,
pena orribile
ch'ogni spirto del cor mi divide
e, pria dello spirar, mi dà la morte.

Morrò misera, sì: vincesti, oh Sorte!
Ma già con piè veloce
sento avanzarsi ad occuparmi il toscio;
vacilla ormai la voce,
lugubre testimone
ch'all'ocaso vicin sian l'ore mie;
tinti d'atro carbone
a' miei lumi i suoi rai presenta il die.
Ahi, fasto, ahi, gioie corte!
Morrò misera, sì: vincesti, oh Sorte!»

Cantata a soprano solo «Amor, m'hai così avinto»
(poetic text by Anonymous)
Amor, m'hai così avinto
a la beltà di quella dea che adoro,
che di lei sempre ingelosito io moro;
e il mio destin sì vole
che non vorrei che la mirasse il sole,
anzi a raggion pavento
che avendo lei qual bianca neve il volto
non resti un dì dai rai del sol disciolto.

Se a guardar bellezze amabili
cento lumi sarian poco,
bramerei forme cangiabili
per trovarmi in ogni loco.
Se a diffendere una venero
poco val Marte alle prove,
per ridur gl'audaci in cenere
bramo i fulmini di Giove.

Ma, almen s'altro non posso,
vorrei che ad ogni istante
fosse cieco in mirarla ogn'altro amante;
anzi, ancor temerei
che se da' lumi suoi
manda la donna mia raggio infocato,
fiamme concepirebbe un cor gelato.

Amanti, quel volto
ch'amor vi mostrò
sappiate che è molto
che a me si donò.
Se il bello che è d'altri
amar non si può,
con occhi sì scaltri
mirarlo perché?

Ah, che se alcun vedessi
mirar la donna mia,
morir tosto vorrei di gelosia
e ho timor sì estremo
che di me ancora ingelosito io temo;
anzi provo in me stesso
che in mirar e adorar sì bei costumi,
son gelosi fra loro il core e i lumi.

Duet «Il nume d'amore»
(«Poesia del Sig. dottore Berselli»)

C & A Il nume d'amore
più/men grave ferita
col ciglio mi fa.
Sì vago/fiero è quel dardo,
che vibra uno sguardo,
che pari tormento/ contento il core
non ha.

C Han sì veloce moto le saette
d'un ciglio e son sì certe
le ferite d'un core
se ad adorar vaga pupilla apprende
che quel momento istesso
in cui gode mirando è quel che
offende.

A No, che se pria d'amare
deve l'occhio che mira
far che il ciglio mirato
osservi il core in così breve istante,
non può l'occhio che vede esser
amante.

C & A Dunque amor le sue facelle
non aduna/tutte aduna in due pupille.
E nel ciel d'un vago volto
sono lampi e sono stelle
poco/semprè amabili e tranquille.

C Sarò sempre costante
a mirar di due luci il bel splendore.

A Avrò l'ali alle piante
per fuggir di due luci il fiero ardore
C & A che lusinga e inganna/che consola e
diletta e l'alma e il core.

Duet *Gelosia invidiosa*
(Giovanni Pietro Monesio, *La musa seria*,
Stamperia di Giuseppe Corvo e Bartolomeo
Lupardi, Rome 1674) [only the first stanza,
with alterations]

Gelosia, co' tuoi sospetti
mille pene all'alma apporti.
Amareggi i miei diletta,
avveleni i miei conforti,
invola agl'occhi miei ogni riposo.
Mai non dorme in amor un cor geloso.

*Edition of the poetic texts by
Federico Lanzellotti*